

Growth rate, sclerotia production, culture type, and virulence of 10 isolates of *R. solani* ^a IIRRI, 1987.

Isolate no.	Host	Culture type ^b	Growth rate ^c (mm/h)	Sclerotia (no./plate)	Virulence ^d (RLH %)
RS9-1	Rice	I	2.9 ab	55 bc	68 abc
RS16-1	Rice	III	2.5 b	55 bc	62 abc
RS26-1	Grass	IV	2.8 ab	9 d	57 bcd
RS27-1	Millet	II	3.2 a	25 cd	75 a
RS44-8	Rice	II	2.8 ab	35 bc	65 abc
RS52-2	Rice	II	2.7 ab	33 c	52 cd
RS64-4	Rice	III	2.8 ab	60 bc	57 bcd
RS68-4	Rice	V	2.9 ab	134 a	74 a
RS72-1	Rice	VI	1.3 c	22 cd	43 d
RS14-3	Rice	IV	2.8 ab	16 cd	72 ab

^aMeans of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bAll the *R. solani* isolates were grouped into six culture types based on the colony color, growth characteristics, size and pattern of sclerotia production in PDA + 0.1% urea medium. ^cGrowth rate was calculated by regression analysis of linear growth over time. ^dVirulence measured as RLH developed in IR58 in 20 d after inoculation. $RLH \% = \frac{\text{lesion height}}{\text{plant height}} \times 100$

grown in pots in the greenhouse with 1.6 g N/30-cm pot. IR58 was inoculated at booting and lesion height and plant height were measured 20 d after inoculation.

The 10 isolates differed in growth rate, sclerotia production, and virulence (see table). Growth rate varied from 1.3 to 3.2 mm/h and sclerotia production from 9 to 134 sclerotia/plate. No

correlation between growth rate and sclerotia production ($r = 0.23$ ns) or between sclerotia production and virulence ($r = 0.37$ ns) was noted. The correlation was significant ($r = 0.78^{**}$) between growth rate and virulence measured as relative lesion height (RLH) in IR58 20 d after inoculation (see figure), but if the extreme values for RS72-1 were excluded, the correlation

Relationship between growth rate of 10 isolates of *R. solani* in agar medium and virulence measured as RLH (%) in IR58. IIRRI greenhouse, 1987.

coefficient becomes nonsignificant ($r = 0.66$ ns). The mean growth rates of the 9 other isolates (excluding RS72-1) do not differ much (2.5 to 3.2 mm/h). Virulence varied from 52 to 75%.

The most virulent isolate (RS72-1) with the highest growth rate was isolated from millet grown during the dry season in an upland field following rice. □

Control of rice pests with phosphamidon 85% WP

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Two rice varieties were planted for four seasons at Ambasamudram in 1984-85 (TKM9 in Jun-Oct and IR20 in Sep-Feb). Phosphamidon at 210 g ai/ha was sprayed in 4 treatments (see table). Gall midge onion shoots, stem borer deadhearts, green leafhoppers, and

whorl maggot leaf damage were counted 45 d after transplanting (DT) in the first planting and 30 DT in the second planting.

Spraying three times was most effective. With only 1 application, 1 spray 20 DT was most effective. □

Effect of phosphamidon 85% WP on rice insect pests in wet lowlands. ^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-85.

Application time (DT)	1984						1985				
	Jun - Oct ^b		Sep - Feb ^c				Jun - Oct ^d		Sep - Feb ^e		
	GM (%)	Yield (t/ha)	GM (%)	GLH (no./5 sweeps)	WM (%)	Yield (t/ha)	GLH (no./5 sweeps)	Yield (t/ha)	GM (%)	SBDH (%)	Yield (t/ha)
-	5.9 b	7.0 b	26.3 c	43 b	12.4 ab	2.8 a	10.9 d	5.4 b	23.6 d	21.7 b	4.1 a
20	1.8 a	6.9 b	15.8 a	21 a	11.2 a	3.2 a	7.2 bc	5.9 b	16.2 c	16.6 a	4.5 a
40	4.6 b	7.0 b	23.7 bc	37 b	14.5 b	4.0 a	7.0 b	5.9 b	12.0 b	14.6 a	4.5 a
60	3.9 a	6.9 b	20.9 b	28 a	11.5 a	3.4 a	9.2 cd	5.9 b	10.1 ab	14.5 a	4.8 a
20,40,60	1.7 a	7.5 a	21.2 b	22 a	13.8 b	3.2 a	5.2 a	6.1 a	8.8 a	15.5 a	4.7 a

^a GM = gall midge, SBDH = stem borer deadhearts, GLH = green leafhopper, WM = whorl maggot. In a column, numbers followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05% level. ^bNo SBDH and GLH infestations. ^cNo SBDH. ^dNo GM and SBDH. ^eNo GLH and WM.